

This is the standard brain model, and goes as followed:

- Seen environmental LSD hallucination, insert seen level, insert seen clock, insert seen generalisation, insert seen specialisation, insert seen outside, insert seen macro, insert seen micro, insert seen nano, insert seen quantum, insert seen dream, insert seen zone, insert seen element, insert seen molecule, insert seen compound, insert seen chemical, insert seen thread, insert seen needle, insert seen sew, insert seen stitch, insert seen swirl, insert seen squiggle, insert seen spiral, insert seen fractal, insert seen pattern, insert seen coordination, insert seen nano particularity, insert seen quantum wonderland, insert seen rune, insert seen orb, insert seen string, insert seen wave, insert seen field, insert seen day, insert seen time, insert seen moment, insert seen second, insert seen minute, insert seen hour, insert seen gap, insert seen cycle, insert seen wall – seen seen environmental LSD hallucination link – insert seen level, insert seen clock, insert seen generalisation, insert seen specialisation, insert seen outside, insert seen macro, insert seen micro, insert seen nano, insert seen quantum, insert seen dream, insert seen zone, insert seen element, insert seen molecule, insert seen compound, insert seen chemical, insert seen thread, insert seen needle, insert seen sew, insert seen stitch, insert seen swirl, insert seen squiggle, insert seen spiral, insert seen fractal, insert seen pattern, insert seen coordination, insert seen nano particularity, insert seen quantum wonderland, insert seen rune, insert seen orb, insert seen string, insert seen wave, insert seen field, insert seen month, insert seen timespace, insert seen moment length, insert seen second width, insert seen minute height, insert seen hour position, insert seen gap area, insert seen cycle volume, insert seen wall – seen environmental LSD hallucination link – insert seen level, insert seen clock, insert seen generalisation, insert seen specialisation, insert seen outside, insert seen macro, insert seen micro, insert seen nano, insert seen quantum, insert seen dream, insert seen zone, insert seen element, insert seen molecule, insert seen compound, insert seen chemical, insert seen thread, insert seen needle, insert seen sew, insert seen stitch, insert seen swirl, insert seen squiggle, insert seen spiral, insert seen fractal, insert seen pattern, insert seen coordination, insert seen nano particularity, insert seen quantum wonderland, insert seen rune, insert seen orb, insert seen string, insert seen wave, insert seen field, insert seen year, insert seen space, insert seen length, insert seen width, insert seen height, insert seen position, insert seen area, insert seen volume, insert seen wall – seen environmental LSD hallucination link – insert seen level, insert seen clock, insert seen generalisation, insert seen specialisation, insert seen outside, insert seen macro, insert seen micro, insert seen nano, insert seen quantum, insert seen dream, insert seen zone, insert seen element, insert seen molecule, insert seen compound, insert seen chemical, insert seen thread, insert seen needle, insert

seen sew, insert seen stitch, insert seen swirl, insert seen squiggle, insert seen spiral, insert seen fractal, insert seen pattern, insert seen coordination, insert seen nano particularity, insert seen quantum wonderland, insert seen rune, insert seen orb, insert seen string, insert seen wave, insert seen field, insert seen decade, insert seen image, insert seen wall – seen environmental LSD hallucination link – insert seen level, insert seen clock, insert seen generalisation, insert seen specialisation, insert seen outside, insert seen macro, insert seen micro, insert seen nano, insert seen quantum, insert seen dream, insert seen zone, insert seen element, insert seen molecule, insert seen compound, insert seen chemical, insert seen thread, insert seen needle, insert seen sew, insert seen stitch, insert seen swirl, insert seen squiggle, insert seen spiral, insert seen fractal, insert seen pattern, insert seen coordination, insert seen nano particularity, insert seen quantum wonderland, insert seen rune, insert seen orb, insert seen string, insert seen wave, insert seen field, insert seen date, insert seen mirror, insert seen wall.

What was explained and shown above was the standard brain model.

This set is timed as 22:52, and is dated as the 9th day of the 2nd month, of the 2025th year.